

Computations of Apparent Formation Constants and Free Metal Ions in EGTA or EDTA Buffer Systems. Part—I : Effects of pH and Metal Concentration with Respect to Ligand

S. D. BISWAS and F. S. CHEBIB

Department of Oral Biology, Faculty of Dentistry, University of Manitoba,
Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada R3E 0W3

Thermodynamic formation constants, ($\log K$) (Bjerrum, Schwarzenbach and Sillen, 1957) for each of four hydrogen and metal bound with ethylene glycol-bis (β -amino ethyl ether) N,N'-tetra-acetic acid (EGTA) or metal bound with ethylenediamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA) were used to compute the following apparent formation constants: $K'_{MeHEGTA}$, $K'_{MeHEDTA}$, K'_{MeEGTA} , and K'_{MeEDTA} . A computer program was developed to calculate these four apparent formation constants for any metal, given its thermodynamic constants, for the full pH range (0.1 to 14.0 at increments of 0.1). A more expanded computer program was developed to calculate, for the same pH range and for any given metal: ligand ratio, the free metal concentration in the solution, given the metal's thermodynamic constants. The program was utilized to calculate for Ca, Mn, Mg, etc. the exact amount of free metal ion for the full pH range and for metal to ligand ratios ranging from 0.01 to 0.1 at 0.01 intervals, for 0.10 to 0.90 at 0.10 intervals and for 0.90 to 0.99 at 0.01 intervals. It was possible to show that the free calcium increased by nearly two-fold when the pH increased by one-tenth order magnitude, i.e. 0.1 pH unit.

CALCIUM is involved in several physiological processes viz., excitation-contraction coupling, action potential of muscle fibre membrane, regulation of enzyme action, etc¹⁻⁵. Highly selective calcium chelating agents e.g. ethylene glycol bis (β -amino ethyl ether) N,N'-tetra acetic acid (EGTA) or ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) are frequently used to regulate free calcium ion concentration in the reaction medium. To determine the calcium ion concentration accurately, the applications of exact conditional or apparent formation constants denoted by $\log K'$ between the metal ion and the ligand are essential because the value of $\log K'$ appears to change as a function of pH. These apparent formation constants are derived from a true or thermodynamic value which, for some metal ions, have been already determined by a number of different methods viz., radioactive tracer⁶, chelex partitions^{5,7}, murexides⁸, arsenazo III⁹, membrane electrode⁹ and more commonly by the pH titrations¹⁰. However, the use of selective membrane electrode is not very uncommon and this is carried out in the presence of varieties of buffer, e.g. imidazole, tris-maleate, phosphate, etc. The value of the true formation constant as determined by the later method agrees reasonably well with that of pH titration value as previously determined by Bjerrum *et al*¹⁰.

The apparent formation constants ($K'_{CaHEGTA}$, K'_{CaEGTA}) are shown to be dependent on pH^{11-13} . For greater accuracy, both these constants have

simultaneously been used to calculate the free calcium ions in this buffer system. Similar calculations were carried out with the EDTA system as well.

In the present investigation, the various formation constants, e.g. K'_{CaEGTA} , $K'_{CaHEGTA}$, K'_{CaEDTA} and $K'_{CaHEDTA}$ have been calculated for the full pH range at 0.1 pH increments and used in computing the amount of free calcium ion concentration in solution of EGTA or EDTA buffer system.

A computer program was developed to calculate free metal ion concentration in a solution at varying pH increments (0.1 to 14.0 at 0.1) and for a given range of metal to ligand ratio. The listing of the source statements of the computer program is presented and the program was coded in Fortran and may be run on most medium to large computers*. The theoretical background used for the program is explained in the next section.

Procedures :

Theoretical background :

The reaction parameters involved in the calculation of free metal ions in Me-EGTA or Me-EDTA buffer system are dealt in two different sections :

(a) Determination of conditional or apparent formation constants ($K'_{MeHEGTA}$, K'_{MeEGTA} , K'_{MeEDTA})

*Detailed program is available on request.

and $K'_{MeHEDTA}$) from respective thermodynamic constants, which have been determined earlier at known ionic strengths of 0.1 M KCl (20°)^{1,6,7}. The conditional constants are pH-dependent. The EGTA or EDTA ligand is a tetrabasic acid and has four dissociable H ions, being able to associate with the ligand stepwise as shown in the following equations :

where L^{4-} , HL^{3-} , H_2L^{2-} , H_3L^- and H_4L^0 are different ionic species, L being the ligand (EGTA or EDTA) and K_{a1} , K_{a2} , K_{a3} and K_{a4} are formation (thermodynamic) constants. The formation constants have been determined under thermodynamic conditions where ionic strength is kept constant in the presence of 0.1 M KCl at 20° (see Table 1).

TABLE 1

Abbreviation for the constant in the text	Cation	Ligand	Thermodynamic EGTA $\log_{10}K$	EDTA $\log_{10}K$
K_{a1}	H ⁺	L ⁴⁻	9.46	10.26
K_{a2}	H ⁺	HL ³⁻	8.85	6.16
K_{a3}	H ⁺	H ₂ L ²⁻	2.68	2.67
K_{a4}	H ⁺	H ₃ L ⁻	~2.00	1.99
K_{MeHL}	Ca ²⁺	HL ³⁻	5.33	3.51
K_{MeL}	Ca ²⁺	L ⁴⁻	11.00	10.70

From Bjerrum, Schwarzenbach and Sillin (1957).

Applying the law of mass action, the above equation can be presented as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} [H_4L^0] &= K_{a4} [H_3L^-] \times [H^+] \\ [H_3L^-] &= K_{a3} [H_2L^{2-}] \times [H^+] \quad \dots (2) \\ [H_2L^{2-}] &= K_{a2} [HL^{3-}] \times [H^+] \end{aligned}$$

and $[HL^{3-}] = K_{a1} [L^{4-}] \times [H^+]$

When bivalent metal such as calcium ligands with different ionic species, several calcium complexes are formed. They are shown as follows :

Hence,

$$[MeH_3L^+] = K_{MeH_3L} [H_3L^-] \times [Me^{2+}] \quad \dots (4)$$

$$[MeH_2L^0] = K_{MeH_2L} [H_2L^{2-}] \times [Me^{2+}] \quad \dots (5)$$

$$[MeHL^-] = K_{MeHL} [HL^{3-}] \times [Me^{2+}] \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\text{and } [MeL^{2-}] = K_{MeL} [L^{4-}] \times [Me^{2+}] \quad \dots (7)$$

where four different types of complexes (MeH_3L^+ , MeH_2L^0), etc. are likely to be formed and each complex will have corresponding formation cons-

tants. The last two formation constants are used to compute conditional formation constants (see Table 1), because the charge acquired by the complex is pH dependent and the metal-ligand complex with a positive charge or with a zero charge exists in negligible quantities at the physiological pH range. Therefore, only conditional formation constants (K'_{MeHL} and K'_{MeL}) have been used. Hence (HL^{3-}) and (L^{4-}) are the ionic species most prevalent at the physiological pH range. These have been calculated and will be published elsewhere.

The logarithms of the thermodynamic formation constants for the interaction of EGTA and EDTA with H ions and calcium as calculated by Bjerrum *et al*¹⁰ are given in Table 1.

(b). Calculation of free calcium ions in the EGTA and EDTA systems :

From equations (6) and (7), we have :

$$K_{MeHL} = [MeHL^-] / [HL^{3-}] \times [Me^{2+}] \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\text{and } K_{MeL} = [MeL^{2-}] / [L^{4-}] \times [Me^{2+}] \quad \dots (9)$$

At a given pH condition the conditional formation constants K'_{MeHL} and K'_{MeL} can be defined as follows :

$$K'_{MeHL} = [MeHL^-] / [L_{total}] \times [Me^{2+}] \quad \dots (10)$$

$$\text{and } K'_{MeL} = [MeL^{2-}] / [L_{total}] \times [Me^{2+}] \quad \dots (11)$$

where $L_{total} = H_4L^0 + H_3L^- + H_2L^{2-} + HL^{3-} + L^{4-}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } R_1 &= K_{MeHL} / K'_{MeHL} \\ &= \frac{[MeHL^-] \times [Me^{2+}] \times [L_{total}]}{[MeHL^-] \times [Me^{2+}] \times [HL^{3-}]} \end{aligned}$$

(where, K_{MeHL} is a thermodynamic constant and K'_{MeHL} is an apparent formation constant).

$$R_1 = \frac{[L_{total}]}{[HL^{3-}]}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} R_1 &= \frac{[H_4L^0] + [H_3L^-] + [H_2L^{2-}] + [HL^{3-}] + [L^{4-}]}{[HL^{3-}]} \\ &= \frac{[H_4L^0]}{[HL^{3-}]} + \frac{[H_3L^-]}{[HL^{3-}]} + \frac{[H_2L^{2-}]}{[HL^{3-}]} \\ &\quad + \frac{[HL^{3-}]}{[HL^{3-}]} + \frac{[L^{4-}]}{[HL^{3-}]} \\ &= K_{a2} \cdot K_{a3} \cdot K_{a4} \cdot [H^+]^3 + K_{a3} \cdot K_{a2} [H^+]^2 + \\ &\quad K_{a2} [H^+] + 1 + 1/[K_{a1} \cdot H^+] \quad \dots (12) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} R_2 &= K_{MeL} / K'_{MeL} = K_{a1} \cdot K_{a2} \cdot K_{a3} \cdot K_{a4} [H^+]^4 + \\ &\quad K_{a1} \cdot K_{a2} \cdot K_{a3} [H^+]^3 + K_{a1} \cdot K_{a2} [H^+]^2 + \\ &\quad K_{a1} [H^+] + 1 \quad \dots (13) \end{aligned}$$

Since, $Me^{2+} + L_{total} = MeL_{total}$, where $K'_{MeL_{total}}$ is the conditional formation constant, therefore,

$$[K'_{MeHL} + K'_{MeL}] = K'_{MeL_{total}} = \frac{[MeL_{total}]}{[Me^{2+}] \times [L_{total}]} \quad \dots (14)$$

MeL_{total} is taken as approximately equal to the

total cations present and the free ligand, L_{total} as approximately equal to the total ligand minus MeL_{total} .

Equation (14) has been written as a quadratic equation to avoid the necessity of successive calculation of the free metal ions. Hence,

$$Me^{2+}[free] = -b \pm \frac{\sqrt{b^2 + 4K'_{MeL_{total}} [MeL_{total}]}}{2K'_{MeL_{total}}} \dots (15)$$

where, $b = 1 + K'_{MeL_{total}} [L_{total} - MeL_{total}]$

Results and Discussion

The conditional or apparent formation constants for calcium computed as a function of pH, are listed in Appendix II¹⁷.

Fig. 1a.

Fig. 1b.

The effects of both pH and the concentration of EGTA on free calcium ions are shown in Figs. 1a and 1b; similar effects with EDTA, another strong chelator of calcium, are shown in Figs. 2a and 2b. Although these studies have been carried out over the full range of pH, in the present graphs only effects are shown between a selected pH range [5.0-8.5], the range over which the pH of the reaction medium could vary physiologically, and at three different ratios of calcium to ligand [Me : EGTA or EDTA, 0.1, 0.5 and 0.9]. Results other than these are listed in Appendix II¹⁷.

Fig. 2a.

Fig. 2b.

From the Figs. 1a and 2a, it is quite evident that as calcium to ligand ratios increase, the free calcium ion concentration concomitantly increase as shown by the fall in pMe values. When Figs.

1a and 2a are compared as an effect of pH, the ligand EDTA seems to behave more effectively as a calcium chelator at least at pH 6.0 than at pH 8.0 and the effect is quite opposite when EGTA is used. Although, one would prefer to use EGTA over EDTA, when magnesium is also present as a part of the reactant, in addition to the presence of a large quantity of calcium ion; in such situations EGTA is more effectively used as a buffer¹⁴, since the magnesium ions could hardly shift the sigmoidal curves (see Figs. 1a or 2a), thus effecting the free calcium ion concentrations in solution significantly. However, in the presence of equally large amounts of magnesium ions one might expect a shift in the sigmoidal curve significant enough to cause a substantial change in the free calcium ion concentrations. One could replot the curve as an effect of magnesium by successive calculations, alternating with calcium and magnesium until a constant free calcium concentration is obtained. Of course, the prevalence of binding of either calcium or magnesium to the ligand will depend upon their respective formation constants. At least for the EGTA, the formation constants for calcium and magnesium are several magnitudes apart and this makes the EGTA a better buffer to be used when calcium and magnesium are both present in solution.

In EGTA, the effect of pH on free pMe is linear within a certain range of pH (between 5.0 and 8.0) as shown in Fig. 1a. However, in EDTA buffer it is slightly curved within the same pH range (see Fig. 2a). The ratio between calcium and ligand does not affect linearity.

Table 2 lists pCa values as computed by the present method, where different values for the formation constants for EGTA were used. These formation constants had been obtained through different techniques using several types of buffers at a constant ionic strength. What is important at this point is to emphasize that the method described by Owen⁹ gave the same value of the formation constant [K_{CaEGTA}] to the magnitude of $10^{11.00}$, as

previously obtained by the potentiometric titration (Schwarzenbach *et al*, 1957). However, other techniques produced formation constants somewhat lower than those reported in the present table. This change in the formation constant will obviously affect the free pCa in solution. If the pCa values are compared with two different constants, one with $10^{11.00}$ and the other with $10^{10.51}$, a substantial difference in the free calcium ions will be obtained. The difference between these two values could go as high as 50-70%.

Weber and Winicur¹⁶ have used dissociation constant rather than the formation constant to calculate the free calcium in solution (K_{diss} being $1.2 \times 10^{-6} M^{-1}$ at pH 6.6). This value was slightly less than what we have calculated with our system i.e., the value at pH 6.6 was $1.29 \times 10^{-6} M^{-1}$. This minor difference in the formation constant would lead to a fair amount of free calcium ion difference. It would be safer to use formation constant of the same pH, the pH at which the reaction is supposed to be carried out. Hence, it was essential to compute the formation constants for each of 0.1 pH-unit change. However, the larger the difference as one might conceivably see between the two values of pH 6.8 and 7.4, a much larger difference in the free calcium is likely to be obtained.

Owen⁹ reported that the formation constant was independent of the buffer solution (e.g. imidazole, tris-maleate or phosphate), in agreement with the findings of Schwarzenbach *et al*¹⁵, but he did not agree with the viewpoint of Ogawa² and Godt⁸, who stated that the formation constant somehow depended upon the type of the buffer used.

The effect of pH on the free calcium is quite substantial and this can be ascertained if free calcium ions are calculated at two different pH values. For example, at pH 7.0, the free calcium ions is in the order of $2.301 \times 10^{-8} M^{-1}$, whereas at pH 6.5, a 0.5 pH-unit less than the former, the free calcium concentration becomes of the order of

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF THE FREE pCa AT DIFFERENT K_{CaEGTA} VALUES

Source	Method	KCl (M)	Buffer	MgCl ~ (mM)	ATP (mM)	pH	K_{CaEGTA} (M^{-1})	$K_{CaHEGTA}$ (M^{-1})	pCa
Schwarzenbach <i>et al</i> (1957)	pH/potentiometric titration	0.1	Phosphate	—	—	varying	$10^{11.00}$	$10^{10.51}$	7.475
Schwarzenbach <i>et al</i> (1957)	pH/potentiometric titration	0.1	Phosphate	—	—	varying	$10^{11.00}$	—	—
Ebashi (1961)	Radioactive tracer	0.14	10 mM Tris-maleate	10	—	6.8	$10^{10.51}$	—	6.785
Briggs and Fleishman (1965)	Chelex partition	0.05	30 mM Imidazole	4	4	6.7	$10^{10.51}$	—	6.805
Ogawa (1968)	Murexide	0.1	20 mM Imidazole	0 or 10	—	6.8	$10^{10.51}$	—	6.825
Godt (1974)	Chelex partition	0.1 to 0.3	22.2 mM Imidazole	5	5	7.0	$10^{10.51}$	—	6.895
Dipolo <i>et al</i> (1976)	Arsenazo III	0.1	2mM TES	25	—	7.0	$10^{10.51}$	—	7.435
Owen (1976)	Ca-membrane electrode	—	Imidazole Tris-maleate or phosphate	—	—	—	$10^{11.00}$	—	7.475

TES, N-tris (hydroxymethyl) methyl-2-aminomethane sulfonic acid.

$2.28 \times 10^{-7} M^{-1}$. At pH 7.5, the value further decreases by an order of magnitude ($2.31 \times 10^{-8} M^{-1}$). Therefore, it is quite conceivable that the application of a more accurate formation constant for the calculation of the free calcium ions is important. Otherwise, a slight difference in the values of the formation constants may add a significant error in the determination of free calcium ions in solution. With a 0.2 pH-unit difference the calcium ions in solution could vary as high as 3 fold. To maintain a required amount of calcium ions in solution for carrying out a specific reaction, the use of Appendix II¹⁷ is recommended to avoid error due to the pH difference.

The added advantage of the present determination is that both the formation constants ($K'_{M\&H}$ and $K'_{M\&L}$) have been simultaneously plugged in the calculation and this will enable the calculation of the free calcium ions to a much greater degree of accuracy. In some instances the effect may not be very large where the pH is low (below pH 7.0), but the effect of the last constant might be pronounced when the pH reaches as high as 8.0 or above.

References

1. S. IMAI and K. TAKEDA, *J. Physiol.*, 1967, 190, 155.
2. Y. OGAWA, *J. Biochem.*, 1968, 64, 255.
3. S. EBASHI and M. ENDO, in "Progress in Biophysics and Molecular Biology", J. A. V. BUTLER and D. NOBLE, (Eds.), 1968, Vol. 18, p. 123, Pergamon Press, London
4. C. CAPUTO, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1968, 51, 180.
5. R. E. GODT, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1974, 63, 722.
6. S. EBASHI, *J. Biochem.*, 1961, 50, 236
7. F. N. BRIGGS and M. FLEISHMAN, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1965, 49, 131.
8. R. DIPOLO, J. REQUENA, F. J. BRINLEY, Jr., L. J. MUL-LINS, A. SCARPA and T. TIFFERT, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1976, 67, 433.
9. J. D. OWEN, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1976, 451, 321.
10. J. BJERRUM, G. SCHWARZENBACH and L. G. SILLEN, "Stability Constants, Part I. Organic Ligands", The Chemical Society, London, 1957, p. 76, 90.
11. H. PORTZEHL, P. C. CALDWELL and J. C. RUEGG, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1964, 79, 581.
12. L. G. SILLEN and A. E. MARTELL, "Stability Constants of Metal-Ion Complexes", Chemical Society Publication, 17, 1964, London.
13. A. RINGBOM, "Complexation in Analytical Chemistry, Chemical Analysis", 1963, Vol. 16, p. 334, Interscience Publications, New York.
14. C. C. ASHLEY and D. G. MOISESCU, *Proc. Physiological Soc.*, 1974, 112P.
15. G. SCHWARZENBACH, H. SENN and G. ANDEREGG, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 40, 1886.
16. A. WEBER and S. WINICUR, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1961, 236, 3198.
17. Appendix II is omitted to economize space ; and can be obtained from the author (S.D.B).